

TECHNICAL REQUIREMENTS
FOR THE DIESEL GENERATOR
MONITORING SYSTEM (DGMS)

Contents

Contents	2
1. General Requirements for DGMS	3
1.1. DGMS Tasks.....	3
1.2. DGMS Architecture.....	4
1.3. Communication Channels	5
2. Software Requirements	6
2.1. General DGMS Software Requirements.....	6
2.3. Dashboard and Report Data Composition	8
2.4. Event List Requirements.....	10
3. Onboard Equipment Requirements.....	11
3.1. General Requirements for Onboard Equipment Components	11
3.2. Functional Requirements for Onboard Equipment.....	12
3.3. Onboard Equipment Design Requirements	13
4. Subscription and Tariffing Requirements.....	14
5. Related Services Requirements	15
6. Manufacturer and Integrator Reputation Requirements.....	16
7. Certification Requirements.....	17

1. General Requirements for DGMS

1.1. DGMS Tasks

1. Fuel consumption monitoring
2. Fuel level monitoring in the tank
3. Engine operating hours tracking
4. Engine load monitoring
5. Monitoring of technical fluid levels and condition
6. Starter battery status monitoring
7. Monitoring of current alternator parameters
8. Generated power monitoring
9. Engine malfunction monitoring and alerts
10. Alternator operating mode monitoring
11. Remote generator control

1.2. DGMS Architecture

DGMS includes:

1. Standard diesel generator sensors – voltage, current, total/active/reactive power, power factor monitoring
2. Diesel generator controller (control unit)
3. Additional sensors – fuel consumption monitoring, engine runtime tracking, fuel level monitoring in the tank
4. Telematics gateway or monitoring terminal
5. Telematics server

Fig. 1 – DGMS Architecture

1.3. Communication Channels

Data is transmitted to the Telematics Server via standard GSM network data channels.

2. Software Requirements

2.1. General DGMS Software Requirements

1. Scalable architecture — supporting up to 10,000 diesel generators without modifying configured functions or reports.
2. Each parameter transmitted, processed, and displayed must be unified with the corresponding onboard equipment parameter to ensure consistent naming and values across the system.
3. Unified parameter format must enable ML/AI-based analysis. A dedicated database must store parameter attributes.
4. Capability to create custom parameters derived from automatic calculations based on real parameters.
5. Data must be separated according to operational tasks (see section 2.3).
6. Data for each generator must be sourced exclusively from a unified, structured functionality module.
7. Must support data acquisition from diesel generators of various brands and engine models, compatible with controllers from different manufacturers.
8. Remote access for integrators, fleet administrators, and operators from any Internet-connected PC.
9. Access via web interface with login/password authentication.
10. Role-based access control according to job responsibilities.
11. Real-time operational data viewing.
12. Generation of analytical reports on generator operation for any selected period.
13. Ability to set route checkpoints and create geofences.
14. Access to at least 90 days of historical data and unlimited archive access.
15. Recovery time after power loss or other non-critical system failure — max 3 minutes.

16. Recovery from hardware failure or critical OS failure — limited to time required for hardware repair and software reinstallation.
17. Prevent operator-induced failures by restricting administrator rights for end users.
18. No scheduled maintenance required for the software.
19. Documentation must include:
 - a. User manual for all fleet-level users.
 - b. Guide for feature selection, configuration, and adaptation to specific operating conditions.

2.2. DGMS Software Interface Requirements

1. User-friendly, intuitive interface for non-IT specialists.
2. Flexible dashboard and report template configuration by the user.
3. Ability to rearrange and resize icons, widgets, and other interface elements.
4. Real-time list of accessible objects and a map with corresponding icons.
5. Clicking an icon displays the current status of the object.
6. Reports must be available in table and chart formats.
7. Multi-parameter graphs (1–3 parameters over time) for any chosen period, with parameter selection from a dropdown list.
8. Graphs must be zoomable on the time axis; hovering over any point shows parameter values, date, and time.
9. Configurable event notifications via pop-up windows.
10. Chart view must support:
 - a. Zooming by selecting a specific area
 - b. Exporting reports to a single PDF file

2.3. Dashboard and Report Data Composition

Engine

1. Fuel feed pressure
2. Engine oil level
3. Engine oil pressure
4. Engine coolant temperature
5. Engine coolant level
6. Engine oil temperature
7. Engine RPM
8. Current engine torque
9. Average engine load
10. Engine start mode
11. Engine torque
12. Fuel feed prohibition status
13. Total engine starts
14. Starter runtime
15. Engine runtime
16. Engine idle runtime

Alternator

1. Alternator rotational speed
2. AC frequency per phase
3. Alternator voltage per phase
4. Alternator current per phase
5. Alternator active power
6. Alternator reactive power
7. Alternator apparent power
8. Alternator apparent power per phase
9. Power factor ($\text{Cos } \varphi$)
10. Power factor ($\text{Cos } \varphi$) per phase
11. Total energy generated
12. Total power output in kWh
13. Overall network power factor
14. Total generator load, % (kW)
15. Total generator load, % (kVA)

Fuel

1. Fuel temperature
2. Hourly fuel consumption
3. Average hourly fuel consumption
4. Total fuel consumption
5. Total idle fuel consumption
6. Total fuel consumption in "Optimal" mode
7. Total fuel consumption in "Overload" mode
8. Total fuel consumption in "Tampering" mode
9. Hourly fuel consumption in "Feed" flowmeter chamber
10. Hourly fuel consumption in "Return" flowmeter chamber
11. Flowmeter runtime
12. Flowmeter idle runtime
13. Flowmeter runtime in "Optimal" mode
14. Flowmeter runtime in "Overload" mode
15. Flowmeter runtime in "Tampering" mode
16. Engine operation mode by fuel consumption
17. Fuel volume in tank
18. Fuel level in tank

Diagnostics

1. Onboard network voltage
2. Onboard network mode
3. Number of emergency reports
4. Number of critical reports
5. Number of informational reports
6. DG set runtime
7. Battery runtime
8. Number of DG restarts
9. Number of satellites
10. Receiver status
11. Antenna status
12. Received signal strength

2.4. Event List Requirements

Engine

1. Ignition ON/OFF
2. Low / high oil pressure
3. Engine overspeed
4. Engine start / stop
5. Failed engine start attempt
6. Emergency engine shutdown

Alternator

1. Overvoltage per phase
2. Undervoltage per phase
3. Overfrequency / underfrequency
4. Overcurrent per phase
5. Overload per phase
6. Low power factor ($\text{Cos } \varphi$)
7. Phase imbalance
8. Overload
9. High earth leakage current

Fuel

1. Refueling
2. Fuel drain from tank
3. Flowmeter tampering
4. Interference with flowmeter operation

Diagnostics

1. Power supply ON/OFF
2. Power supply OFF
3. Loss / acquisition of satellite signal
4. Onboard network overvoltage / undervoltage
5. Emergency button pressed
6. Onboard network fault

3. Onboard Equipment Requirements

3.1. General Requirements for Onboard Equipment Components

The onboard equipment (OE) set may include, but is not limited to:

1. Telematics Gateway or Monitoring Terminal:
 - 1.1 GPS/GLONASS location acquisition
 - 1.2 CAN J1939 interface support
 - 1.3 RS-485 interface support (Modbus RTU protocol)
 - 1.4 Configurable reporting system for transmission to the Telematics Server
 - 1.5 Onboard detection of rapid events (before server transmission)
 - 1.6 Report transmission via SMS, e-mail, GSM 2G, LTE — direct, without server
2. Fuel Flow Meter:
 - 2.1 CAN J1939 interface
 - 2.2 Power supply from onboard network and internal power source
 - 2.3 Built-in self-diagnostics
 - 2.4 Measurement correction according to environmental conditions
 - 2.5 Data storage in internal memory
3. Fuel Level Sensor:
 - 3.1 CAN J1939 interface
 - 3.2 Measurement correction according to environmental conditions
 - 3.3 Calibration table stored in internal memory (fuel level vs. fuel volume)
 - 3.4 Water-in-tank detection with alarm transmission
4. CAN and RS-485 Data Converters:
 - 4.1 CAN J1939 and RS-485 Modbus interfaces
5. Contactless CAN and RS-485 Readers:
 - 5.1 Installation without cutting into bus wiring
6. Digital-to-Analog Converters:
 - 6.1 Simultaneous conversion of analog-to-digital and digital-to-analog signals
7. CAN Bus Display:
 - 7.1 Data viewing from CAN J1939 interface and additional sensors
 - 7.2 Flexible display configuration — assigning names to parameters
 - 7.3 Parameter grouping

The exact OE set is determined by the monitoring tasks for the specific DGMS installation.

All devices must be connected via a single cable (bus) with sealed connectors and T-adapters, providing both power supply and configuration access through the same cable.

3.2. Functional Requirements for Onboard Equipment

Additional onboard equipment must provide the following onboard functions:

1. Location Tracking:
 - 1.1 Location logging with date/time stamps, route recording, and travel distance calculation
 - 1.2 Detection of movement start/stop, travel time, number of movements, and stops/parking events
2. Fuel Tank Monitoring:
 - 2.1 Direct fuel level measurement in one or multiple tanks
 - 2.2 Fuel volume calculation using stored calibration table
 - 2.3 Detection of refueling and fuel drains
 - 2.4 Measurement of fuel temperature in tank
3. Fuel Consumption and Engine Runtime Monitoring:
 - 3.1 Direct measurement of hourly fuel consumption
 - 3.2 Calculation of fuel consumption for a given period
 - 3.3 Calculation of runtime for a given period
4. Engine Operating Parameter Monitoring:
 - 4.1 Reading engine RPM from CAN bus
 - 4.2 Reading coolant temperature from CAN bus
 - 4.3 Reading oil pressure from CAN bus
5. Remote Engine Control:
 - 5.1 Diesel engine start
 - 5.2 Diesel engine stop

If fuel tampering is detected, the fuel level sensor and fuel flow meter must transmit a special message containing: event timestamp, type of tampering, duration of tampering, quantitative impact (e.g., drained volume, flowmeter interference time, other measured values).

3.3. Onboard Equipment Design Requirements

1. Telematics Gateway or Monitoring Terminal:
 - 1.1 Materials ensuring minimum service life of 5 years
 - 1.2 Powered by onboard network and internal power source
 - 1.3 Sealable to prevent tampering
 - 1.4 Complete mounting kit included
2. Fuel Flow Meter:
 - 2.1 **Measuring chamber made of ZAMAK alloy or brass (service life \geq 5 years)**
 - 2.2 Built-in replaceable dirt filter
 - 2.3 Powered by onboard network and internal power source
 - 2.4 Sealable to prevent tampering
 - 2.5 Complete mounting kit included
3. Fuel Level Sensor:
 - 3.1 **Capacitive type, \leq 1 kg to prevent tank deformation**
 - 3.2 Dirt protection filter and water short-circuit prevention in tubes
 - 3.3 Rigid top and bottom mounting to prevent movement in installation hole
 - 3.4 **Materials ensuring service life \geq 5 years**
 - 3.5 Powered by onboard network
 - 3.6 Sealable to prevent tampering
 - 3.7 Complete mounting kit included
4. CAN and RS-485 Data Converters:
 - 4.1 **Materials ensuring service life \geq 5 years**
 - 4.2 Powered by onboard network
 - 4.3 Sealable to prevent tampering
5. Contactless CAN and RS-485 Readers:
 - 5.1 Visual operating mode indication
 - 5.2 **Materials ensuring service life \geq 5 years**
 - 5.3 Powered by onboard network
 - 5.4 Sealable to prevent tampering
6. Digital-to-Analog Converters:
 - 6.1 **Materials ensuring service life \geq 5 years**
 - 6.2 Powered by onboard network
 - 6.3 Sealable to prevent tampering
7. CAN Bus Display:
 - 7.1 **Materials ensuring service life \geq 5 years**
 - 7.2 Powered by onboard network
 - 7.3 Sealable to prevent tampering

4. Subscription and Tariffing Requirements

1. Chargeable DGMS service packages include dashboards (real-time operation monitoring) and reports (data analysis for a selected period).
2. Services are provided by subscription for a specific object or group of objects, granting access to predefined dashboard and report templates.
3. Templates include a predefined set of data units (monitored parameters from a specific source).
4. Service cost is determined by the composition and number of provided data units.
5. The service package can be adapted to different object configurations and required number of monitored parameters.
6. DGMS services are available for generators of various brands, any engine models, and control units from different manufacturers.
7. Services are provided on a paid basis with daily tariffing.

5. Related Services Requirements

1. **Warranty.**
 - Fuel level sensors — 36 months
 - Fuel flow meters — 30 months
 - Electronic system components — minimum 24 months
2. **Installation.** Installation of onboard equipment must be performed by an integrator's specialists certified by the manufacturer.
3. **After-Sales Service.** Availability of certified manufacturer service centers in the operating region to provide both warranty and post-warranty servicing.
4. **User Training.** Option to train the customer in installation, connection, configuration, and operation of the equipment, conducted by certified integrator specialists.
5. **Technical Support.** Provided by the integrator or the manufacturer for at least 16 hours during working days.
6. **Documentation.** All onboard equipment must include a detailed installation, configuration, and operation manual.

6. Manufacturer and Integrator Reputation Requirements

1. Manufacturer's experience in producing fuel level sensors and fuel flow meters — at least 15 years.
2. Manufacturer's experience in producing other electronic DGMS components — at least 5 years.
3. Integrator's experience in installing and configuring the proposed DGMS onboard equipment — at least 3 years.
4. No ongoing legal proceedings for debt recovery or bankruptcy against either the integrator or the manufacturer.
5. Manufacturer must confirm that the onboard equipment was purchased by the integrator directly from the manufacturer or from an official distributor.

7. Certification Requirements

1. All onboard equipment must comply with the international standard ISO 7637 "Road vehicles – Electrical disturbances from conduction and coupling" and/or national standards based on ISO 7637.
2. Fuel level sensor must have a Certificate of Approval for the type of measuring instrument.
3. If DGMS onboard equipment from different manufacturers is used, a certificate confirming equipment compatibility must be provided.